

DEALING WITH DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOURS OF STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSES.

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Abstract. *Misbehaviours occur almost in each class, and experienced teachers will competently cope with it. Although, there are many types of misbehaviour, it is a complex thing to control misbehaviour and to teach the new topic and build a stable relationships with them being a young teacher. So this article aimed to discuss the strategies to deal with the disruptive behaviour of students, coping with the relationship between teachers and students, and how to manage in the English foreign language (EFL) classroom effectively. Furthermore all researches related to this will be provided and discussed in literature review of this article.*

Keywords; *misbehaviour, EFL classroom, teachers, students, deal with, strategies and tips.*

Introduction

English is becoming the world-wide used language, and to provide for the citizens standards of education, English is taught from nursery schools to advanced universities in every country. However, teaching English for children and adults requires special effort from teachers. In Uzbekistan English is taught as foreign language, and in preschool institutions and in primary schools it is taught as simple as it can be with different games, songs, poems to improve the listening and speaking skills of students. While playing games or singing songs, students mostly misbehave and teacher get angry and tries to shout and struggle with their behaviour. In secondary and high schools and universities, students misbehaviour happens from not knowing the language well, and misunderstanding of the lesson material. It is

such a difficult thing for teachers to deal with the misbehaviours of students, get ready the materials for the lesson. Teaching grammar, vocabulary, speaking, listening, writing and other skills adequately for the students. This article aims to provide all types of misbehaviour of students and give a proper strategies for teacher to handle students disruptive behaviours in EFL classes.

Literature review

In-class communication is negatively impacted by "misbehaviour," which is defined as behaviour that obstructs the "teaching-learning process," but a teacher's negative attitude to changing this conduct may lead to an unstable classroom atmosphere. As the fundamental aim to educate people is to change their behaviour occurring in classes later in the society widely. The environment of the students play a big role in formation of the behaviour and only if the classroom climate structured appropriately and rules set by teachers obeyed fully by students and teacher, the misbehaviour may be stopped to exist.[1]

In a study which was comparative analysis in three countries, namely China, Australia and Israel, all teachers from these countries complained for students' misbehaviour in classes. According to the research, chinese students demonstrate respect for their teacher and classroom misbehaviour are quantitatively less than in other two countries. Teachers in Australia and Israel show aggressive and mostly punitive actions, such as yelling to students and in this way they lose respect of their students and other factors are also can be influenced in this situation. Chinese teachers are less punitive and make more discussions on classroom topics and listen to students opinions, however there are still several disruptive behaviour are appeared. [2]

Students misbehavior also may differ according to the gender of a teacher. Students display aggressive and verbal actions while female teachers educating. Although male educators were autocratic and directive in teaching style, students demonstrate less disruptive behaviours during the lesson. The methods to handle

with the misbehavior were warning, ignoring, keeping an eye on students, conversating individually with students, talking to parents and warning administration about the problems in students' misbehavior.[3]

Teacher's strategies to cope with the classroom misbehavior are studied in the following research. Teacher's strategies were:

1. Using classroom rules.
2. No punishment.
3. Body- language.
4. Increasing volume.
5. Being positive. [4]

It is clear that classroom rules arrange students behaviours in positive way, although not punishing students seemed strange, but by giving punishment, in teachers' opinion, may lead to more aggressive reactions of students, body language such as keeping eye contact with bullying student, increasing the intonation to warn students that the teacher is getting angry from the noise of students, being positive and friendly can make students respect teachers and change the attitude towards the subject of that teacher. Another scholar also provided similar findings according to his results studies typically concentrate on using collaborative and problem-solving techniques, and most of the techniques stressed adopting different teaching strategies and approaches depending on the classroom context, educating and equipping teachers to deal with students' disruptive actions, and developing reciprocal dialogue and contact with students to address their bad behaviors. It is not advised to use avoidance and punishment techniques like kicking students out of class or making fun of them. Successful growth, familiarity with unusual circumstances, and classroom management abilities can result from having knowledge and skills regarding education and developing effective communication in the classroom. Since disrespectful and threatening behavior, contempt for teachers, and even little

privacy violations in the classroom can have a big impact on learning environments, it is important to avoid these behaviors.[5]

Lack of interest, motivation and attention, negative classroom environment, society, and family also teachers'inappropriate attitude towards the students personality can be the causes of disruptive behaviour. According to [6] dealing with these problems can be when teacher works with each student individual and deal with it intellegently by thinking deeply. In order to face those problems more successfully, new L2 teachers must keep in mind that being at ease in their own skin, having a solid strategy, and understanding how to operate with the setting will all help. In the long run, paying close attention to what functions well in the classroom and what doesn't. Being metacognitive will enable L2 teachers to make judgments that will result in good classroom management. With time, CM is probably going to turn into their ally so, be assured, knowledgeable, prepared, adaptable, neat, and reflective.[7] According to [8, 9] The instructional component of lesson planning involves the efforts made by teachers to arrange students into groups and seat them, control routines, time activities, set up and sequence tasks, give instructions, offer feedback, and keep an eye on the students. On the other side, the learner behavior management dimension comprises such as activities that foster learner self-regulation and prevent, correct, and redirect incorrect student behavior.

However, coping with misbehaviors of students is obligatory not only for teachers but also for society, parents and administrative section of the school. Chinese teacher's lack in having extra assistance in coping with students bad behaviour as they lack of administration in the teaching system of the country.[10]

Conclusion

To sum up the article, there are different types of disruptive behaviours of students and the main causes are lack of interest, motivation, attention and so on. Different strategies are utilized to correct the bejaviour of students and most of them were keeping an eye contact, working individually with students, talking to parents

and etc. Furthermore, the gender of teacher also played a role in demonstration of misbehavior, as students displayed more distractive manners in female teachers lesson.

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